

RESULTS OF RECONSTRUCTIVE AND RESTORATIVE SURGERY IN PATIENTS WITH ILEOSTOMY USING TRADITIONAL TREATMENT APPROACHES

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ABSTRACT

According to the World Health Organization (WHO) and randomized controlled trials, there is a persistent global trend toward an increase in the number of surgical interventions that are forcibly completed with the formation of ileostomies, more than half of which are performed in patients of working age [7;8]. At the same time, the formation of an ileostomy is often accompanied by complications, permanent disability, and severe psychological disorders, which significantly reduce the social status and quality of life of patients. These factors complicate the surgical rehabilitation of patients with ileostomies, leading to decreased quality of life and impaired social adaptation. Elimination of the stoma and performance of the reconstructive stage occupy a leading position in the surgical rehabilitation of this category of patients.

Relevance of the problem. According to the World Health Organization (WHO) and randomized controlled trials, there is a persistent global trend toward an increase in the number of surgical interventions that are forcibly completed with the formation of ileostomies, more than half of which are performed in patients of working age [7;8]. At the same time, the formation of an ileostomy is often accompanied by complications, permanent disability, and severe psychological disorders, which significantly reduce the social status and quality of life of patients. These factors complicate the surgical rehabilitation of patients with ileostomies, leading to decreased quality of life and impaired social adaptation. Elimination of the stoma and performance of the reconstructive stage occupy a leading position in the surgical rehabilitation of this category of patients.

However, the problem of a high incidence of anastomotic failure remains alarming, reaching 20–30%, with mortality rates ranging from 6% to 35% [1;3;4;9].

Currently, more than 500 techniques and modifications of manual suturing methods and more than 100 types of suture materials have been described. An ideal anastomosis should also be easy to perform, reproducible, and simple to master [5]. Analysis of the literature shows that

over recent decades, new methods for restoring intestinal continuity and preventing postoperative complications have been developed and described [2;6].

Clinical experience indicates that the known methods of forming ileotransverse anastomoses (ITA) are not free from certain drawbacks, which justifies the need for further research and improvement. Solving these problems will improve surgical treatment outcomes in this category of patients.

Aim of the study. To improve the results of surgical treatment of intestinal diseases by optimizing surgical tactics.

Materials and methods. The present study included 93 patients with diseases of the colon who underwent right-sided hemicolectomy with formation of an end ileostomy followed by reconstructive and restorative surgery (RRS) in the form of ileotransverse anastomosis (ITA) at the Clinic of Andijan State Medical Institute.

According to the objectives of the study, patients were conditionally divided into two groups:

- Comparison group (2021–2022): 54 patients (58.1%) with urgent intestinal diseases and ileostomy formation treated using traditional approaches;
- Main group (2023–2024): 39 patients (41.9%) with urgent intestinal diseases and ileostomy formation treated using optimized surgical tactics.

The distribution of patients was carried out according to the WHO International Age Classification (2021).

To achieve the study objectives, general clinical, laboratory, biochemical, instrumental, and statistical research methods were applied in accordance with protocols approved by the Ministry of Health of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

Results and discussion. In accordance with the study objectives, the comparison group (2021–2023) included 54 patients (58.1%) with colonic diseases who underwent right-sided hemicolectomy with end ileostomy followed by formation of an ileotransverse anastomosis using traditional treatment approaches.

The distribution of patients was carried out according to the WHO International Age Classification (2021).

In the comparison group, males accounted for 38 patients (70.4%) and females for 16 patients (29.6%). The majority of patients were aged 45–59 years—35 patients (64.8%), representing the most economically active population, which has significant medical and economic implications. Patients aged 60 years and older accounted for 13 patients (24.1%), while those aged 19–44 years accounted for only 6 patients (11.1%), which also has important medical and social significance.

In the comparison group, the predominant patient population consisted of those with colonic tumors—43 patients (79.6%), which significantly complicated the determination of surgical tactics. Among them, males accounted for 28 patients (51.8%) and females for 15 patients (27.8%). Patients with non-neoplastic colonic diseases accounted for 7 patients (7.5%), including 2 males (3.7%) and 1 female (1.8%). Traumatic injuries of the colon were observed in 8 patients (14.8%), including 5 males (9.3%) and 3 females (5.5%).

The most common tumor localizations were the cecum—18 patients (45.0%) and the hepatic flexure—14 patients (35.0%). Tumors of the lower third of the colon were detected in

3 patients (7.5%), the middle third in 2 patients (5.0%), and the upper third in 3 patients (7.5%).

The extent of oncological disease was determined according to the international TNM classification system (7th edition, adopted in 2009 and recommended for use since 2010).

In the comparison group, stage II colon cancer (T3–4N0M0) was diagnosed in 33 cases (82.5%), and stage III (T1–4N1–2M0) in 7 cases (17.5%). Notably, stage I and stage IV tumors were not observed in this group. All patients exhibited a complicated course of colon cancer.

Patients with colon tumors predominantly presented with clinical manifestations of acute intestinal obstruction (AIO) in the subcompensation stage—22 patients (55.0%) and decompensation stage—14 patients (35.0%). In 4 patients (10.0%), AIO was accompanied by tumor perforation and development of purulent peritonitis.

Non-neoplastic colonic diseases were observed in 3 patients (5.5%), including complications of appendicular infiltrate in 1 patient and dolichocolon in 2 patients. In 8 patients (14.8%), the indication for surgery was abdominal trauma, including road traffic accidents with multiple ruptures of the colon and its mesentery resulting in impaired blood supply to the intestinal wall (7 cases), as well as stab and incised wounds of the colon with purulent peritonitis (1 case), which necessitated right-sided hemicolectomy with formation of an end ileostomy.

Among concomitant therapeutic conditions, anemia was the most common, occurring in 10 cases (18.5%), which was associated with colon tumors. Cardiovascular diseases ranked second in frequency—6 cases (11.1%), including ischemic heart disease, arrhythmias, and postinfarction cardiosclerosis. Obesity was observed in 3 cases (5.6%), respiratory system diseases in 4 cases (7.4%), hepatobiliary system diseases in 2 cases (3.7%), and urinary system diseases in 1 case (1.9%). The presence of severe concomitant pathology significantly complicated surgical decision-making and postoperative rehabilitation.

Among concomitant surgical conditions, cholelithiasis was observed in 1 case (1.8%), ventral hernias in 2 cases (3.7%), ovarian cysts in 4 cases (7.4%), and uterine fibroids in 3 cases (5.6%).

As noted, the study included only patients who had previously undergone right-sided hemicolectomy with the formation of an end ileostomy. At the same time, 16 patients (29.6%) had their primary surgical interventions performed in other medical institutions of the Andijan region. Prior to admission for reconstructive and restorative surgery (RRS) in the form of ileotransverse anastomosis (ITA), the patients were under continuous outpatient follow-up.

The duration of stoma-bearing before RRS ranged from 1.5 to 3 months and from 3 to 6 months in only 3 patients (5.6%) each, respectively. In the comparison group, the duration of stoma-bearing before RRS was 7–12 months in 37 patients (68.5%) and more than 12 months in 11 patients (20.4%).

The analysis showed that in the comparison group, performance of RRS at early stages (from 1.5 to 6 months) was significantly limited, although in 6 patients (11.1%) the indication for end ileostomy formation was non-neoplastic colonic diseases, as well as injuries and trauma of the colon.

It should be noted that in the comparison group, when the duration of stoma-bearing was 7–12 months and the indication for end ileostomy formation was colon cancer, RRS was performed in 29 patients (53.7%), which carries a high risk of tumor recurrence.

In addition, when the duration of stoma-bearing was 12 months or more, RRS was performed in 8 patients (14.8%) with colonic injuries and trauma, which we consider to be an unjustified and delayed restoration stage. These circumstances were taken into account in the course of our work in patients of the main group.

In the comparison group, early complications developed in 17 cases (31.5%), including suppuration and infiltration of the stomal wound in 6 patients (11.1%), peristomal dermatitis in 5 patients (9.3%), and skin hypergranulation in 6 patients (11.1%).

The analysis demonstrated that the high frequency of skin complications in the comparison group was associated with traditional approaches to prevention and treatment, as well as with the enzymatic characteristics of the small intestine. It should be noted that in the comparison group, stoma-related complications such as bleeding, necrosis, eventration, prolapse, and abscess formation were not observed.

Late stomal complications were diagnosed in 7 cases (13.0%), including ileostomy retraction in 1 case (1.8%), evagination in 4 cases (7.4%), and cicatricial-atrophic changes in 2 cases (3.7%). In the comparison group, the development of late stomal complications had a significant negative impact on the surgical rehabilitation of patients.

As is well known, the method of ileotransverse anastomosis (ITA) formation plays an important role in surgical rehabilitation and its outcomes after right-sided hemicolectomy with the formation of an end ileostomy. The methods of ITA formation in patients of the comparison group are presented in Table 3.10.

In the studied patients, side-to-side ileotransverse anastomosis was performed in 25 cases (46.3%), end-to-side anastomosis in 12 cases (22.2%), and invagination end-to-side ITA in 9 patients (16.7%).

The main drawback of the proposed invagination anastomosis was the connection of non-homologous tissues and the possibility of invaginate eversion with complete obstruction of intestinal patency in cases of excessive invaginate length. It should be noted that in recent years we have developed a “submerged” invagination end-to-side ITA technique, which was performed in 8 patients (14.8%).

A retrospective analysis of the results showed that in cases of colonic tumors, reconstructive and restorative surgery (RRS) was performed within 7–12 months in 29 patients (53.7%). Of these, tumor recurrence occurred in 7 cases (13.0%), requiring hospitalization in an oncology center for re-resection with repeated formation of an end ileostomy, despite the fact that patients had undergone chemotherapy under oncological supervision.

In this regard, when the primary indication for right-sided hemicolectomy with end ileostomy formation was a colonic tumor, this subsequently became the basis for performing RRS no earlier than 12 months after the initial surgery. Along with adjuvant chemotherapy, colonoscopy with biopsy and histological examination was performed prior to RRS, and reconstructive surgery was indicated only in the absence of atypical cells.

Thus, as experience accumulated and based on a retrospective analysis of the results in the comparison group, when the primary cause was a colonic tumor, reconstructive and restorative surgery (RRS) was performed in more than 12 months in 27 out of 29 patients (69.2%), whereas only 2 cases (5.1%) underwent RRS within 12 months.

In non-tumor-related diseases, in 8 cases (14.8%) the timing of RRS was unjustifiably delayed. Despite the fact that in these patients the postoperative period was not accompanied by the development of skin or stomal complications and no comorbid conditions were present, RRS was postponed. Therefore, in the main group, in similar clinical situations, we consider it justified to perform RRS within 1.5 to 3 months.

For non-tumor-related diseases, as well as traumatic injuries of the colon, the indications for RRS were expanded, with surgery performed within 1.5–3 months in 8 patients (20.5%) and within 3–6 months in 1 patient (2.6%). In this group, only the diagnosis of skin and stomal complications, as well as comorbid conditions after ileostomy formation, served as reasons for refraining from RRS within 3 months in 1 case (2.6%) and within 8 months in 1 case (2.5%).

In the comparison group, a comparative evaluation of the results revealed that in 37 cases (68.5%) ileotransverse anastomosis (ITA) was performed using “traditional” techniques: side-to-side in 25 patients (46.3%) and end-to-side in 12 patients (22.2%). It should be emphasized that it was precisely in this group of patients that the postoperative period was complicated by life-threatening complications.

Comparative analysis demonstrated that in the main group, during RRS, we completely abandoned traditional ITA techniques due to dissatisfaction with treatment outcomes. Consequently, in the main group, all patients underwent ITA using invagination techniques. Of these, end-to-side invagination ITA was performed in 8 patients (20.5%), “submerged” invagination end-to-side ITA in 15 patients (38.5%), and “submerged” invagination end-to-end ITA in 16 patients (41.0%).

Summary. Thus, a retrospective analysis of the results of surgical treatment in this patient cohort within the comparison group revealed certain shortcomings, limitations, and omissions associated with traditional surgical approaches. These findings served as the basis for the development of a more effective method of ileotransverse anastomosis formation, as well as for the creation and implementation of an improved diagnostic and therapeutic algorithm aimed at optimizing surgical tactics

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